

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHMED SHAHZADH bearing USN 6SU20IV001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDIVYA DINESHAN bearing USN 6SU20IV002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIDHA FATHIMA P N bearing USN 6SU20IV003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHIMA S bearing USN 6SU20IV004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsRESHMI P bearing USN 6SU20IV005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSREYA SHAJI bearing USN 6SU20IV006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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